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WS-ARC SERVICE CONFIGURATION MANUAL

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1 Introduction

The Web Service (WS) Advanced Resource Connector (ARC) provides a great deal of services which all share a common configuration interface. One or more services can be specified in a configuration and the `arched` daemon should then be used for starting the service(s). The configuration should be specified in a file using either the relatively simple INI format, or the more complex XML format.

INI configuration is the recommended way of configuring services for people who are new to ARC or unfamiliar with WS-ARC configuration. However it is limited in the sense that it relies on profiles. A profile is a configuration template setup for one or more services, and common use case profiles exist for most services and are installed per default. The limitation lies in the fact that only services and options which are specified in the profile can be configured in INI configuration, however the installed profiles should give enough flexibility for common use cases. For a detailed description on INI configuration see section 2. Profiles are further discussed in section 4.

XML configuration is the core format of WS-ARC configuration – it is used internally – and thus it gives full flexibility when configuring services. A detailed description of XML configuration can be found in section 3.

The `arched` daemon, which is used to start WS-ARC services according to the configuration is briefly discussed in section 5.

1.1 How to read this manual

This manual is divided into the three independent sections INI configuration, XML configuration and Profiles, and these can be read independent of each other. Additionally the `arched` section describe the command with the same name.

It should be noted that words typeset with the `typewriter` font should be typed as written.

2 INI configuration

As mentioned in the introduction, INI configuration directly relies on profiles, and a profile is a configuration template setup for one or more services. So when creating a INI configuration file a choice of profile must be made. Only one profile can be used in a given INI configuration. A standard WS-ARC installation comes with a set of profiles and the list in appendix A gives a short description of these. The profiles will per default be installed into the `/usr/share/arc/profiles` folder, where it is also possible to find an example INI configuration file for each of the profiles.

A INI configuration file basically consist of sections, attribute-value pairs and maybe comments and blank lines. In the following code-listing the syntax of an INI configuration file is shown:

```
# A comment
[ common ]
profile = <profilename> or <path-to-profile>

<attribute> = <value>
...
...

# Another comment
[ <section-name> ]
<attribute> = <value>
...
...
[ <another-section> ]
<attribute> = <value>
...
...
```

A section is specified by putting the name of the section inside brackets ([and]), where the left bracket ([) must be the first non white space character on the line. Any white space character after the left bracket and before the right will not be part of the section name. Every attribute-value pair belongs to the section which has been defined previously. If the file starts without declaring a section, then following attributes will belong to the common section. Multiple sections with identical names are different sections, except for the common section, which is special in this respect and if multiple common sections exist these will be considered as one.

The `profile` attribute is also special, as it is used to indicate which profile the INI configuration uses. Its value should either be the name of a WS-ARC profile (no `xml` suffix), see appendix A or it should be the absolute path to a profile (with `xml` suffix). The `profile` attribute must be located in the common section. If multiple `profile` attributes exist only the first attribute will be used.

Attribute-value pairs are defined by specifying the name of the attribute followed by an equal sign and then the value the attribute should take. It is the first equal sign which separates the attribute from the value. If a line, not defining a section, does not contain an equal then it will be ignored and if it contains multiple equal signs then all but first equal sign will be part of the value. Any white space before and after the attribute and value will be ignored. Only attributes which have been defined in the selected profile will be considered by `arched`. For each profile in WS-ARC a corresponding INI configuration file exist which defines sensible values and at the time list all configurable attributes. When it comes to multiple attributes with identical names defined in the same section, it is the selected profile which determines if multiple attributes is allowed and will be interpreted or not. It is possible that attributes from one section can override attributes from another section, however this behaviour is completely determined by the profile.

Comments in the INI configuration file are specified by letting the first non white space character be the sharp character (#), and these will be ignored by `arched`.

2.1 Examples

2.1.1 Echo service

```
profile = /usr/share/arc/profiles/EchoService.xml

pidfile = /tmp/arched.pid
logfile = /tmp/arched.log
loglevel = INFO

port = 60000

cacert = /etc/grid-security/certificates
host_cert = /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem
host_key = /etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem

[ echo ]
prefix = {{
suffix = }}
```

2.1.2 Other service

2.2 Limitations

Configuring WS-ARC services in INI format may pose some limitations, since this configuration format depend on profiles. If one wants to configure a service setup which is not covered by any of the available profiles, it is simply not possible to configure that service setup in INI format and one has to use the XML format described in section 3. It should however be noted that it is easy to switch from INI to XML format since the `arched` command provide a way to convert a INI configuration into XML. See section 5 for further details.

3 XML configuration

3.1 Overview

XML configuration in WS-ARC provides full flexibility for configuring services, and to construct an adequate configuration one need to address the following subjects. If not done already, a choice on which service(s) being setup need to be made and a short discussion of the available WS-ARC services is given in section 3.2. Upon the choice of service(s) the proper message chain need to be configured and a discussion about message chains is given in section 3.3. Most people also want some kind of security setup capable of allowing/denying certain users, which can be done with security handlers and is discussed in section 3.4. Common configuration options like specifying plugins required for instance by the message chain, and configuring logging, is discussed in section 3.6. In section 3.7 example XML configuration files are given.

3.2 Service configuration

The following services are part of WS-ARC and specific configuration details for these are given in the respective references below:

A-REX - configuration manual in "The ARC Computational Job Management Module - A-REX" [5],

Chelonia storage multi-service - "Chelonia Administrator's Manual" [9],

ISIS distributed P2P information service - "ARC Information System" [6],

Charon authorization service - currently described in "Security Framework of ARC NOX" [15],

HOPI lightweight HTTP webserver - "The HOPI Manual" [8] and also partially described in "Chelonia Administrator's Manual" [9].

3.3 Message Chain

To configure WS-ARC services, a basic knowledge about how these are communicating with clients or other services is needed. WS-ARC uses a chain of message components (MCCs) which serves different levels of functionality. In one end it accepts messages from an interface and in the other a service processes them and produce a response. Two types of MCCs exist, and they differ in that the first type should be able to listen on some interface for messages, while the other simply receives messages from another MCC. The MCC then process the message and pass it on to a single or multiple other MCCs or services. MCCs should be configured using the XML element `Component`, where the `name` attribute specifies the MCC to use. The following MCCs are part of WS-ARC:

`tcp.service` Listens on the TCP interface, see section 3.3.1,

`tls.service` Adds encryption layer to communication, see section 3.3.2,

`http.service` Processes HTTP messages, see section 3.3.4,

`gsi.service` Processes GSI messages as implemented in Globus toolkit [4], see section 3.3.3,

`soap.service` Processes SOAP messages, see section 3.3.5.

Additionally a special MCC, the Plexer, exists which is able to pass messages to different components simply based on the endpoint the messages was sent to, and it should be configured using the `Plexer` element, see section 3.3.6. In the end of the chain a service should be specified, using the `Service` element, where the `name` attribute indicates the given service.

A working configuration should then link a set of MCCs and services, starting with a MCC that receives messages from some interface. The MCCs and services should be uniquely identifiable, by setting the `id` attributes of these elements. A MCC links to another or several MCCs or services using the `next` element, where the `id` attribute specifies the `id` of that MCC or service. Some MCCs support multiple `next` elements

with textual label inside. Those are used by such MCCs to perform internal routing of processed message. But most MCCs do not do any routing and hence require single `next` without label.

The message chain should be contained in the root element `ArcConfig`, which is shown in the conceptual configuration example below:

```
...
<Component name="mcc1.service" id="mcc1">
  <next id="mcc2"/>
</Component>
<Component name="mcc2.service" id="mcc2">
  <next id="service"/>
</Component>
<Service name="service" id="service"/>
...
```

For readability the message chain can be grouped into a `Chain` element in one or more levels.

More technical information about available MCCs and the messages their process may be found in the Hosting Environment technical manual [3].

3.3.1 TCP MCC

The TCP message component is named `tcp.service` and should be the first component in a chain. It is used to setup a server socket which will listen for incoming connections. The socket can be configured using the `Listen` element, which can occur multiple times and under each element the following child elements can be specified:

Interface This element specifies the interface which socket should listen on. If this element is not specified then the socket will listen on all available interfaces.

Port The port which the socket should bind to should be specified with this element. If no port is specified an error will be reported and this `Listen` element will be ignored.

Version The IP version can be specified by this element, and by default both version 4 and 6 will be used. It is possible to specify version 4 or 6 only.

NoDelay By default Nagle's algorithm is used for sending data, however if the `NoDelay` element is set to `true` data will be sent when ready. This is mainly used for optimizing connections for communication patterns which involve a lot of very short messages exchanged by service and client.

Timeout Specifies how much time, in seconds, data sending or receiving may take. If time is exceeded MCC reports error and in most cases connection is dropped. The default value is 60 seconds.

It is also possible to put a limit on number of incoming connections, and how these should be handled if the limit is reached. The limit can only be put on all configured interfaces, and not per interface. The `Limit` element specifies the limit on incoming connections, and the `drop` attribute specifies whether new connections, above the limit, will be put on hold (default) or if they should be dropped, which is specified by setting the attribute to `true`.

An example of a TCP MCC configuration using the described elements is shown below:

```
...
<Component name="tcp.service" id="tcp">
  <Listen>
    <Interface>w.x.y.z</Interface>
    <Port>44444</Port>
    <Version>4</Version>
    <NoDelay>true</NoDelay>
    <Timeout>120</Timeout>
  </Listen>
  <Listen>
```

```

    <Interface>a:b:c:d:e:f:g:h</Interface>
    <Port>55555</Port>
    <Version>6</Version>
    <NoDelay>>false</NoDelay>
    <Timeout>20</Timeout>
  </Listen>
  <Limit drop="true">30</Limit>
</Component>
...

```

3.3.2 TLS MCC

A security layer can be configured with the TLS MCC, named `tls.service`, which is based on the OpenSSL library [2], and it should be put on top of a TCP MCC. By default it is able to understand the SSLv2 (handshake only), SSLv3 and TLSv1 protocols, however the `Handshake` element can be used to specify another behaviour. The supported values for the `Handshake` element are `TLS` (default) and `SSLv3`, where specifying the latter will configure a MCC which only understand the SSLv3 protocol. If other values than the mentioned ones are given, then TLS will be used.

For the TLS MCC to function, it should have access to a host key-certificate pair. The key should be the private one, and it should not be password protected. The path to the key-certificate pair can be specified by using the `KeyPath` and `CertificatePath` elements. If the `KeyPath` element is not specified the default path `/etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem` will be used, and likewise if the `CertificatePath` element is not specified the default path `/etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem` will be used. The supported key and certificate formats are PEM and DER.

When establishing a connection with a client, the client certificate are per default verified against the Certificate Authority (CA) certificates, known to the TLS MCC. The CA certificates used for verification can be specified with either the `CACertificatesDir` or the `CACertificatePath` element, or both elements can be used. The `CACertificatesDir` element should point to a directory containing one or more CA certificates (in PEM format). The files should each contain exactly one certificate, and should be named by the hash value of the CA subject name. CA certificates provided by NorduGrid uses this option. The `CACertificatePath` element should point to a file containing one or more CA certificates (in PEM format) identified by:

```

-----BEGIN CERTIFICATE-----
... (CA certificate in base64 encoding) ...
-----END CERTIFICATE-----

```

sequences. If both elements have been specified, CA certificates will first be looked up in the file pointed to by the `CACertificatePath` element and then in the directory pointed to by the `CACertificatesDir` element. If none of the two elements have been specified, then the `CACertificatesDir` element will be initialised to the `/etc/grid-security/certificates` location. Client certificate verification can also be skipped, which is done by setting the `ClientAuthn` element to `false`.

```

...
<Component name="tls.service" id="tls">
  <KeyPath></KeyPath>
  <CertificatePath></CertificatePath>
  <CACertificatePath></CACertificatePath>
  <CACertificatesDir></CACertificatesDir>
  <ClientAuthn></ClientAuthn>
  <Handshake>SSLv3</Handshake>
</Component>
...

```

If element `CACertificatesDir` have attribute `PolicyGlobus` set to "true" additional verification of client credentials is performed. Client credentials are restricted to be signed by specific Certification Authorities

as specified in additional configuration files. Those files are stored in the location specified by the element `CACertificatesDir` and have names made of the hash of the subject of CA certificate followed by `.signing_policy` suffix. Information about format of those files may be found at http://dev.globus.org/wiki/Signing_Policy

3.3.3 GSI MCC

At its purpose MCC is similar to TLS described in section 3.3.2. It provides security layer using Globus implementation of GSS-API and corresponding communication protocol.

Its configuration element `KeyPath` and `CertificatePath` are identical to those of TLS MCC. This MCC is implemented using libraries of Globus Toolkit and its functionality and requirements are better to be described by description of Globus `gssapi` library.

Use of this MCC is not recommended due to non-standard origin of underlying protocol.

3.3.4 HTTP MCC

The HTTP protocol is supported by the HTTP MCC named `http.service`, and it should either be put on top of the TCP or TLS MCC. A working configuration of this MCC is simple, since it should only use the `next` element. Differently from most other MCCs this one may have multiple `next` with content being name of HTTP method in uppercase. Depending on method client requested message may be routed to different components. Most services of WS-ARC support GET and PUT for data communication and POST for SOAP. Some also support HEAD.

An example of a HTTP MCC configuration is shown below.

```
...
<Component name="http.service">
  <next id="component1">GET</next>
  <next id="component2">POST</next>
  <next id="component3">PUT</next>
</Component>
...
```

3.3.5 SOAP MCC

SOAP is supported by the SOAP MCC, named `soap.service`. It parses and processes incoming messages as SOAP messages. This component should be put right after the HTTP MCC in the message chain. The component is needed by most of the services in WS-ARC. The only option which should be configured for the SOAP MCC is to which component or service the valid SOAP messages should be directed to, and it is done with the `next` element as for the other components.

3.3.6 Plexer

The Plexer is a special MCC which filters messages based on their URL endpoints. It supports multiple `next` elements with content being regular expressions (POSIX extended) used to filter incoming messages. The message is forwarded to the component or service specified by the `id` attribute of the corresponding `next` element which matched the endpoint URL of the message. At the first match the message will be forwarded to the respective component or service and no more expressions will be tried. The `next` elements are tried in order they are specified in configuration. If the message did not match any of the regular expressions then it is discarded and an error is returned to the client. An example of a Plexer configuration is shown below.

```
...
<Plexer>
  <next>~/arex$/</next>
  <next>~/[eE][cC][hH][oO]$/</next>
</Plexer>
...
```

3.4 Security Handlers

Security Handlers are components which extract security related properties of the message, collect them and use for making authorization decisions.

The Security Handlers are assigned MCCs and are arranged in queues. Each queue is processing specific messages. Usually MCCs implement two queues named "incoming" and "outgoing" for the messages going through chain to service and returning back respectively.

The Security Handlers in each queue are applied sequentially and if any produces negative result processing stops and error is raised.

The Security Handlers are added to MCCs through `SecHandler` configuration element put inside `Component` or `Service` elements. The `name` attribute specifies which plugin to be used. And queue is specified by `event` attribute. Each configured instance can be optionally assigned identifier through `id` attribute. The content of `SecHandler` is specific for every kind of plugin. Example is below:

```
...
<Component name="mcc1.service" id="mcc1">
  <next id="mcc2"/>
  <SecHandler name="handler1" event="incoming" id="id1">
  </SecHandler>
</Component>
...
```

For more technical information about security-related attributes of the message and the Security Handlers please see [15].

3.4.1 ARC Authorization

This Security Handler applies set of Policy Decision Point (PDP) element to the message and then produces decision result using combining algorithm specified in `action` attribute of `SecHandler` element. For description of PDP elements see section 3.5. The plugin name of this Security handler is `arc.authz` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

Available combining algorithms are:

breakOnDeny - processing stops when PDP returns Deny decision. The `SecHandler` produces negative result. This is a default algorithm.

breakOnAllow - processing stops when PDP return Allow decision. The `SecHandler` produces positive result.

breakAlways - processing stops after first PDP. Produced result is used as result of `SecHandler`.

breakNever - all PDPs are applied. Result of last PDP is used as result of `SecHandler`.

Here is an example of of ARC Authorization Security Handler configuration.

```
...
<SecHandler name="arc.authz" event="incoming" id="authz">
  <PDP name="arc.pdp">
  ...
  </PDP>
  <PDP name="xacml.pdp">
  ...
  </PDP>
</SecHandler>
...
```

3.4.2 Identity Mapping

The Identity Mapping plugin applies set of associated PDPs to the message being processed and depending on result assigns local account to the message. Its plugin name is `identity.map` and it resides in `identitymap` loading module.

This Security Handler works in a similar way to ARC Authorization (see section 3.4.1). But instead of passing results of PDPs as final processing result it applies local account mapping algorithm associated with particular PDP.

Configuration is also similar with only difference being that inside each PDP configuration element there is additional element representing mapping algorithm used for producing local account name. Available are following mapping algorithms:

`LocalName` - maps to specified account name.

```
...
  <PDP name="arc.pdp">
    <LocalName>nobody</LocalName>
    ...
  </PDP>
...
```

`LocalList` - uses subject of X.509 certificate presented by client to perform mapping. Element content provides path to local file containing pairs of subjects and account names. One pair per line separated by blank space.

```
...
  <PDP name="arc.pdp">
    <LocalList>/etc/grid-security/grid-mapfile</LocalList>
    ...
  </PDP>
...
```

`LocalSimplePool` - manages dynamic mapping of X.509 client subject to a set of local account names. Content of element point to directory containing file named `pool`. This file contains list of local account available for mapping one per line. This directory is also used for storing currently active mappings.

```
...
  <PDP name="arc.pdp">
    <LocalSimplePool>/etc/grid-security/mappool</LocalSimplePool>
    ...
  </PDP>
...
```

3.4.3 Delegation Collector

This plugin processes chain of X.509 certificates and extracts embedded policies. Policies are attached to the message and may be later used by Delegation PDP described in section 3.5.7. The plugin name of this Security Handler is `delegation.collector` and it resides in `mcctl`s loadable module. It has no configuration parameters.

3.4.4 UsernameToken

The UsernameToken Security Handler processes information in the SOAP Header stored according to "Web Services Security UsernameToken Profile 1.0" [11]. The plugin name of this Security Handler is `usnametoken.handler` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

The configuration element **Process** defines type of processing to be performed. Possible values are:

extract - parse and process elements in SOAP Header. This option should be used for service side configuration.

generate - create UsernameToken. This option is only used for client side.

Only another configuration element relevant for service side processing is **PasswordSource**. It specifies path to local file containing list of usernames and passwords (one pair per line) which are accepted by plugin. If there is no pair in file matching one SOAP Header this Security Handler will raise an error.

3.4.5 X.509 Token

The X.509 Token Security Handler processes information in the SOAP Header stored according to "Web Services Security: X.509 Token Profile 1.0" [12]. The plugin name of this Security Handler is `x509token.handler` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

The configuration element **Process** defines type of processing to be performed. Possible values are:

extract - parse and process elements in SOAP Header. This option should be used for service side configuration.

generate - create X.509 Token. This option is only used for client side.

In **extract** mode this plugin process X.509 Token from SOAP Header and validates contained credentials against locally stored CA certificates. Following configuration elements specify location of trusted CA certificates:

CACertificatePath - path to file containing CA certificate.

CACertificatesDir - path to directory containing files with CA certificates.

If provided credentials failed verification this Security Handler will raise an error.

3.4.6 SAML Token

The SAML Token Security Handler processes information in the SOAP Header stored according to "Web Services Security: SAML Token Profile 1.1" [10]. The plugin name of this Security Handler is `samltoken.handler` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

The configuration of this plugin is identical to previously described X.509 Token Security Handler. It supports configuration elements **Process**, **CACertificatePath** and **CACertificatesDir**.

The information collected by this plugin may then be used in ARC Policy Decision Point and Service Invoker Policy Decision Point plugins.

3.4.7 SAML Single Sign-On

3.5 Policy Decision Points

The Policy Decision Point component is responsible for applying particular policy or any kind of authorization evaluation algorithm to properties of the message and providing authorization decision which then used by other components - usually by the Security Handlers implementing functionality of Policy Enforcement Point.

3.5.1 Allow

This PDP always returns positive result. Its plugin name is `allow.pdp` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

3.5.2 Deny

This PDP always returns negative result. Its plugin name is `deny.pdp` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

3.5.3 Simple List

This PDP matches X.509 subject of client certificate to list of predefined values. Its plugin name is `simplelist.pdp` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

Multiple configuration elements `DN` specify accepted subjects. Also attribute `location` may be used to point to a file containing list of subjects, one per line. If client's subject is not listed neither in `DN` nor in `location` PDP returns negative result. Otherwise result is positive. Below is configuration example for simple authorization by grid-mapfile:

```
...
  <PDP name="simplelist.pdp" location="/etc/grid-security/grid-mapfile">
    <DN>/O=Grid/O=NorduGrid/CN=Service Admin</DN>
  </PDP>
...
```

3.5.4 ARC

This plugin applies authorization policy written in ARC Policy language to attributes of the message. Its plugin name is `arc.pdp` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module. For more information about ARC Policy language please see "Security Framework of ARC NOX" [14]. That document also describes security attributes produced by different components of ARC which can be included in policies.

The configuration element `PolicyStore` specifies locations of policy. Its `Location` subelement provides path to file storing policy. Also policy can be directly embedded into configuration by using `Policy` configuration element.

The `PolicyCombiningAlg` element specifies how results from multiple policies are combined. For detailed explanation please refer to [14].

It is also possible to limit number of message attributes which are matched to policy using `Filter` configuration element. This may be needed to achieve better evaluation performance. The multiple subelements `Select` and `Reject` allow to either use only specific attributes or remove specific attributes. If neither `Select` nor `Reject` are specified then all attributes are used.

Example of simple ARC PDP reading policy from external file is below:

```
...
  <PDP name="arc.pdp">
    <PolicyStore>
      <Location>/etc/grid-security/policy.xml</Location>
    </PolicyStore>
  </PDP>
...
```

3.5.5 GACL

This PDP shares configuration parameters and provides functionality similar to ARC PDP described in the section 3.5.4. Its plugin name is `gACL.pdp` and it resides in the same `arcshc` loadable module.

This plugin accepts policies written in GACL instead of ARC language. For more information about GACL please check "The Gridsite Web" [7] and "GACL Mini-Howto" [1].

3.5.6 XACML

This plugin's configuration and functionality are similar to previously described ARC and GACL PDPs. Its plugin name is `xacml.pdp` and it resides in the same `arcshc` loadable module.

This plugin accepts policies written in subset of XACML language [13]. Currently XACML functionality is not complete yet. For more information see [14].

3.5.7 Delegation

This plugin applies authorization policy written in ARC Policy language and obtained from cahin of X.509 Proxy Certificates of client to attributes of the message. Its plugin name is `delegation.pdp` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

Functionality wise it is very similar to ARC PDP described in section 3.5.4 but uses policy internally obtained from message. Hence it has only `Filter` configuration element.

For detailed explanation how policy document is embedded into X.509 Proxy Certificate please refer to [14].

3.5.8 Service Invoker

This plugin communicates with possibly remote authorization service by passing it authorization request and getting back authorization decision. Its plugin name is `pdp.service.invoker` and it resides in `arcshc` loadable module.

The configuration element `Filter` is similar to those in other PDPs.

To specify service to be contacted `ServiceEndpoint` element is used. It contains contact URL of service. Service is expected to accept SOAP over HTTP(S) messages conforming to protocol defined in `TransferProtocol` configuration element. Possible options are `arc` for ARC own protocol and `saml` for "SAML 2.0 Profile of the XACML 2.0" kind of exchange. The format of payload - authorization request and response - is controlled using `RequestFormat` element. Implemented are `xacml` and `arc` options for XACML conforming or ARC specific formats respectively.

For establishing TLS communication channel to the service PDP needs to apply X.509 credentials. For that configuration elements `CertificatePath` and `KeyPath` are used. Alternatively if PDP uses X.509 Proxy Certificate path to file containing proxy may be specified in `ProxyPath`.

For verifying credentials presented by service trusted CA certificates are specified through `CACertificatePath` and `CACertificatesDir` for single file and directory containing multiple files respectively.

3.6 General Daemon Configuration

The following options configures the `arched` daemon, and thus applies to all services. Some of the options can also be set using command line arguments, and if used these will override the configuration file options. See section 5 for a description of the `arched` daemon.

Under the `Server` element the file to store the PID in, can be specified using the `PidFile` element, if not specified the PID will be stored in the file `/var/run/arched.pid`. This options can also be set using a command line argument. If the `Foreground` element is present under the `Server` element, `arched` will run in foreground and thus the `PidFile` element will be ignored. It is also possible to specify that `arched` should run in foreground on the command line, however it is not possible to specify that it should run as a daemon, if configured to run in foreground in the configuration file. Also under the `Server` the user and group owning the `arched` process can be specified, which is accomplished with the `User` and `Group` elements. These can also be set on the command line.

Logging options should be specified under the `Logger` element under the `Server` element. The `File` element specifies which file to write log messages to and if not present log messages will be written to the `/var/log/arc/arched.log` file. Each log message is associated with a log level which indicates the severity of the message. The following log levels exist in WS-ARC, ordered by severity: `FATAL`, `ERROR`, `WARNING`, `INFO`, `VERBOSE` and `DEBUG`. With the `Level` element the level of messages being reported can be specified.

Log messages with a higher or same level as specified by the `Level` element will be written to the log file. The default log level is `WARNING`.

The log messages are also assigned different domains. Domain is a string indicating where message came from. Domains follow hierarchical layout with top level called `Arc` and subdomains added to it separated by dot - like `Arc.MCC.TCP`. It is possible to assign different logging levels to different domains by using multiple `Level` elements each with `Domain` attribute containing affected domain name. The `Level` without `Domain` is assigned to `Arc` domain and is inherited by all other domains unless they have their levels specified explicitly.

By default the log file is not limited in size, neither will any log rotation be done. The `Maxsize` and `Backups` elements can be used to change this behaviour. The `Maxsize` element sets the maximum file size of the log file in bytes, while the `Backups` element specifies the number of files used for log rotation. When the size of the log file exceeds the limit specified by the `Maxsize` element the log file is renamed to `<log-file>.1`. If this file exist it is renamed to `<log-file>.2` and so forth up to the number specified by `Backups`, which means that the last file will be deleted. The log file size is only allowed to exceed the specified limit by the size of one log message. If the `Maxsize` element have been specified and no `Backups` element is specified then log rotation will not be carried out, thus the log file is truncated when the limit is exceeded.

By default log file is kept continuously open. For compatibility with external log rotating utilities it is possible to force log file being closed after every log record is written and re-opened for new one. For that optional `Reopen` element is used. If set to `true` it turns compatibility mode on.

Plugins which should be used later in the configuration should be specified under the `Plugins` element where the `Name` element specifies the name of the plugin. The `Path` element under the `ModuleManager` element specifies where to locate the plugins.

The following example show the use of the above configuration options:

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<ArcConfig>
  <Server>
    <PidFile>/tmp/arched.pid</PidFile>
    <User></User>
    <Group></Group>
    <Logger>
      <File>/tmp/arched.log</File>
      <Level>WARNING</Level>
      <Level Domain="Arc.MCC.TCP">DEBUG</Level>
      <MaxSize>1000000</MaxSize>
      <Backups>5</Backups>
      <Reopen>>false</Reopen>
    </Logger>
  </Server>
  <ModuleManager>
    <Path>/usr/lib/arc</Path>
  </ModuleManager>
  <Plugins>
    <Name>plugin1</Name>
    <Name>plugin2</Name>
    ...
  </Plugins>
  ...
</ArcConfig>
```

3.7 Examples

3.7.1 Echo Service

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<cfg:ArcConfig xmlns="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/loader/2009/08"
  xmlns:cfg="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/arcconfig/2009/08"
```

```

        xmlns:tcp="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/tcp/2009/08"
        xmlns:tls="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/tls/2009/08"
        xmlns:echo="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/echo/2009/08"
        xmlns:infosys="http://www.nordugrid.org/schemas/infosys/2009/08"
    >
<cfg:Server>
  <cfg:PidFile>/tmp/arched.pid</cfg:PidFile>
  <cfg:Logger>
    <cfg:File>/var/log/arc/arched.log</cfg:File>
    <cfg:Level>WARNING</cfg:Level>
  </cfg:Logger>
</cfg:Server>
<ModuleManager>
  <Path>/usr/lib/arc</Path>
</ModuleManager>
<Plugins>
  <Name>mcctls</Name>
  <Name>mcchttp</Name>
  <Name>mccsoap</Name>
  <Name>mcctcp</Name>
</Plugins>
<Chain>
  <Component name="tcp.service" id="tcp">
    <next id="http"/>
    <tcp:Listen>
      <tcp:Interface>0.0.0.0</tcp:Interface>
      <tcp:Version>4</tcp:Version>
    </tcp:Listen>
  </Component>
  <Component name="http.service" id="http">
    <next id="soap">POST</next>
    <next id="plexer">GET</next>
  </Component>
  <Component name="soap.service" id="soap">
    <next id="plexer"/>
  </Component>
  <Plexer id="plexer">
    <next id="echo">/Echo</next>
  </Plexer>
  <Service name="echo" id="echo">
    <echo:prefix>[</echo:prefix>
    <echo:suffix>]</echo:suffix>
  </Service>
</Chain>
</cfg:ArcConfig>

```

4 Profiles

In WS-ARC the concept of profiles have been introduced. A profile is a complete XML configuration template, for a specific service setup and it is used when configuring services in INI format. The core of WS-ARC uses an XML struture for service initialization, which makes the XML format the apparent choice for configuration. However the XML language is not simple and easy to use, which is why WS-ARC utilizes profiles, namely to provide a configuration format (the INI format) easy to use.

To write a profile, some knowledge on the INI (see section 2) and XML configuration formats (see section 3) is needed. Not necessary to say, knowledge on the desired service setup is also needed. A XML configuration file is only a profile if it defines a option mapping from INI format to XML, thus making it possible to utilise the XML configuration through the INI format.

Two XML attributes have been introduced to be able to create a mapping, and these are `inisections` and `initag`. XML elements which should be configurable in INI format must specify these attributes.

The `initag` attribute defines the name of the tag which represent the respective XML element in the INI configuration file, and the `inisections` attribute is used to specify, as a space separated list, which sections the tag can occur in. The list is ordered, in the sense that the listed sections is searched, in the specified order, for the tag specified by the `initag` attribute, and if found in a section no further sections will be searched. Only leaf XML elements (elements with no child elements) should be mapped, mapping non leaf element result in a undefined behaviour. A profile example of a XML element mapping is shown in the listing below:

ElementMapping.xml

```
...
<Server>
  ...
  <Logger>
    <File inisections="special common"
        initag="logfile">/var/log/arc/arched.log</File>
    ...
  </Logger>
</Server>
...
```

And this example profile can then be utilised in a INI configuration file as:

ElementMapping.ini

```
profile=ElementMapping.xml
logfile=/etc/arc/arched.log
...
[ special ]
logfile=/var/arc/arched.log
...
```

And the resulting XML configuration will look like:

```
...
<Server>
  ...
  <Logger>
    <File>/var/arc/arched.log</File>
    ...
  </Logger>
</Server>
...
```

To be able to map XML attributes the use of a new XML element `AttributeRepresentation` have been introduced. The element should have three attributes set, the two attributes `inisections` and `initag` used as described above, and a new attribute `id` which specifies which attribute of the parent element is being mapped. A profile example of a XML attribute is shown in the listing below:

AttributeMapping.xml

```
...
<Component name="tcp.service">
  ...
  <Limit drop="false">
    <AttributeRepresentation id="drop" inisections="common" initag="drop"/>
    100
  </Limit>
</Component>
...
```

And this example profile can then be utilised in a INI configuration file as:

AttributeMapping.ini

```
profile=AttributeMappingExample.xml
drop=true
...
```

And the resulting XML configuration will look like:

```
...
<Component name="tcp.service">
  ...
  <Limit drop="true">100</Limit>
</Component>
...
```

5 The arched daemon

The **arched** daemon is the daemon which is used to host every service in WS-ARC. It will load a configuration file, and host the services specified herein.

arched [OPTION...]

(ARC 0.9)

<code>-f, --foreground</code>		run daemon in foreground
<code>-c, --xml-config</code>	<i>path</i>	full path of XML configuration file
<code>-i, --ini-config</code>	<i>path</i>	fill path of INI configuration file
<code>-d, --config-dump</code>		dump generated XML configuration
<code>-p, --pid-file</code>	<i>path</i>	full path of PID file
<code>-u, --user</code>	<i>user</i>	user name
<code>-g, --group</code>	<i>group</i>	group name
<code>-s, --schema</code>	<i>path</i>	full path of XML schema file
<code>-h, --help</code>		Show help options

If no configuration file is specified, **arched** first looks for the `/etc/arc/server.ini` INI configuration file if it does not exist then the `/etc/arc/server.xml` XML configuration file is tried. If none of these is found **arched** will abort with an error and exit code 1.

A INI configuration file can be specified with the `-i` option, while the `-c` option makes it possible to specify a XML configuration file. If both options are given, the INI configuration will be chosen.

arched also has the capability of printing the XML configuration which will be generated from a given INI configuration. By specifying the `-d` option along with the `-i` option and the path to the INI configuration **arched** will transform the INI configuration to XML and dump the output to standard out and exit.

A List of standard profiles in WS-ARC

A.1 A-REX

ComputingElementWithFork MINIMAL configuration template for a secure standalone Computing Element (CE) with a fork queue.

InsecureComputingElement

ComputingElementWithMapfile

ComputingElementWithMapfileAndPBSBackend

ComputingElement_DNlist

ComputingElement_VOMS

A.2 Chelonia

CheloniaAllCentralizedAHash

CheloniaAllCentralizedAHashWithISIS

CheloniaAllReplicatedAHash

CheloniaAllReplicatedAHashGatewayVOMSWithISIS

CheloniaAllReplicatedAHashWithISIS

CheloniaReplicatedAHash

CheloniaShepherdWithHopi

InsecureNonDistributedStorageElement

NonDistributedStorageElement_DNlist

NonDistributedStorageElement_VOMS

A.3 ISIS

InsecureP2PIIS

InsecureStandaloneIIS

P2PIIS

StandaloneIIS

A.4 Charon

Charon

A.5 Hopi

Hopi

HopiInsecure

HopiWithPlexer

HopiWithPlexerInsecure

A.6 Combined services

InsecureComputingAndStorageElement

ComputingAndStorageElement_DNlist

ComputingAndStorageElement_VOMS

A.7 Testing

Echo

EchoInsecure

EchoPython

EchoPythonInsecure

EchoSAMLToken

EchoUsernameToken

EchoX509Token

InsecureHopiService

B Profile attributes naming convention

Since profiles defines a mapping of XML elements or attributes to INI tags, they control the naming of the tags. So for consistency tags in different profiles representing the same XML element or attribute should not be named differently. A naming convention list for the XML elements and attributes described in section 3 is presented below. Note that there are only conventions for leaf XML elements (element with no children).

XML element/attribute	INI tag	Default value
/Server/PidFile	pidfile	/var/run/arched.pid
/Server/User	user	None
/Server/Group	group	None
/Server/Logger/File	logfile	/var/log/arc/arched.log
/Server/Logger/Level	loglevel	WARNING
/Server/Logger/Maxsize	logmaxsize	None
/Server/Logger/Backups	logbackups	None
/ModuleManager/Path	libpath	None
/Plexer/next	endpointpattern	None
TCP MCC		
/Component/Listen/Interface	interface	0.0.0.0
/Component/Listen/Port	port	60000
/Component/Listen/Version	ipversion	None
/Component/Listen/NoDelay	nodelay	false
/Component/Listen/Timeout	timeout	None
/Component/Limit	limit	None
/Component/Limit.drop	drop	None
TLS MCC		
/Component/KeyPath	x509_host_key	/etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem
/Component/CertificatePath	x509_host_cert	/etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem
/Component/CACertificatePath	x509_cacert_path	None
/Component/CACertificatesDir	x509_cacert_dir	/etc/grid-security/certificates
/Component/ClientAuthn	clientauthn	true
/Component/Handshake	handshake	TLS

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